

MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD APPROACH TO LEAST ABSOLUTE DEVIATION REGRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Least Absolute Deviation (LAD) regression is an important tool used in numerous applications throughout science and engineering, mainly due to the intrinsic robust characteristics of LAD. In this chapter, we show that the optimization needed to solve the LAD regression problem can be viewed as a sequence of Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLE) of location. Requiring weighted medians only, the new algorithm can be easily modularized for hardware implementation, as opposed to most of the other existing LAD methods which require complicated operations such as matrix entry manipulations. Simulation shows that the new algorithm is superior in speed to Wesolowsky's algorithm, which is simple in structure as well. In this paper, Maximum likelihood approach to least absolute deviation regression were discussed.

Keywords: Least Absolute Deviation, Optimization, Maximum Likelihood Estimates, Wesolowsky's algorithm.

1 INTRODUCTION

Least Absolute Deviation (LAD) regression is an important tool used in numerous applications throughout science and engineering, mainly due to the intrinsic robust characteristics of LAD. In this chapter, we show that the optimization needed to solve the LAD regression problem can be viewed as a sequence of Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLE) of location. Requiring weighted medians only, the new algorithm can be easily modularized for hardware implementation, as opposed to most of the other existing LAD methods which require complicated operations such as matrix entry manipulations. One exception is Wesolowsky's direct descent algorithm, which among the top algorithms is also based on weighted median operations. Simulation shows that the new algorithm is superior in speed to Wesolowsky's algorithm, which is simple in structure as well. The new algorithm provides a better trade off solution between convergence speed and implementation complexity.

2 MODEL

The simple LAD regression problem is formulated as follows. Consider N observation pairs (X_i, Y_i) modelled in a linear fashion

$$Y_i = aX_i + b + U_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad \dots (1)$$

where a is the unknown slope of the fitting line, b the intercept, and U_i are unobservable errors drawn from a random variable U obeying a Zero-Laplacian distribution

$$f(U) = (1/2\lambda)e^{-|U|/\lambda} \text{ with variance } \sigma^2 = 2\lambda^2.$$

The LAD regression is found by choosing a pair of parameters a and b that minimizes the objective function mean

$$F(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^N |Y_i - aX_i - b| \quad \dots (2)$$

which has long been known to be continuous and convex. Moreover, the cost surface is of a polyhedron shape, and its edge lines are characterized by the sample pairs (X_i, Y_i) .

The minimization of the LAD cost function is closely related to the location estimation problem defined as follows. Let the random variable V be defined as $V = U + \mu$, where μ is an unknown constant location and U obeys the Laplacian distribution. The MLE of location on the sample set $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^N$ is

$$\mu^* = \arg \min_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^N |V_i - \mu| \quad \dots (3)$$

The solution to the above minimization problem is well known to be the sample *Median*

$$\mu^* = MED(V_i)_{i=1}^N \quad \dots (4)$$

The striking similarity between (2) and (3) infers that, for a fixed $a = a_0$, the minimizer of (2), say $b^*_{a_0}$, is essentially an MLE for location under the Laplacian assumption. For reasons that will be explained shortly, the minimizer of (2) $a^*_{b_0}$, given $b = b_0$, is also an MLE for location under the Laplacian assumption with certain extensions. Thus, a very intuitive way of solving the LAD regression problem can be constructed as a “seesaw” procedure: first, hold one of the parameters a or b constant, optimize the other using the MLE concept, then alternate the role of the parameters, and repeat this process until both parameters converge.

3 ALGORITHM

Consider the linear regression model in (1). If the value of ‘ a ’ is fixed at first, say $a = a_0$, the objective function (2) now becomes a one-parameter function of b :

$$F(b) = \sum_{i=1}^N |Y_i - a_0X_i - b| \quad \dots (5)$$

Assuming a Laplace distribution for the errors U_i , the above cost function reduces to an ML estimator of location for b . That is, we observe the sequence of random samples $\{Y_i - a_0X_i\}$, and the goal is to estimate the fixed but unknown location parameter b . Thus according to (4), the parameter b^* in this case can be obtained by

$$b^* = MED(Y_i - a_0X_i)_{i=1}^N \quad \dots (6)$$

If, on the other hand, we fix $b = b_0$, the objective function reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} F(a) &= \sum_{i=1}^N |Y_i - b_0 - aX_i| \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N |X_i| \left| \frac{Y_i - b_0}{X_i} \right| - a \end{aligned} \quad \dots (7)$$

Again, if the error random variable U_i obeys a Laplacian distribution, the observed samples $\{(Y_i - b_0)/X_i\}$ are also Laplacian distributed, but with the difference that each sample in this set has different variance. The reason is obvious since for each known X_i and zero-mean U_i , U_i/X_i remains a zero-mean Laplacian with variance scaled by $1/X_i^2$. Thus the parameter a^* minimizing the cost function (7) can still be seen as the ML estimator of location for a , and can be calculated out as the *weighted median*.

$$a^* = MED \left(\left| X_i \right| \diamond \frac{Y_i - b_0}{X_i} \Big|_{i=1}^N \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

where \diamond is the replication operator. For a positive integer $|X_i|$, $|X_i| \diamond Y_i$ means Y_i is replicated $|X_i|$ times. When the weights $|X_i|$ are not integers, the computation of the weighted median is outlined.

A simple and intuitive approach to the LAD regression problem is through the following iterative algorithm.

(1) Set $k = 0$. Find an initial value a_0 for a , such as the LS solution.

(2) Set $k = k + 1$ and obtain a new estimate of b for a fixed a_{k-1} using

$$b_k = MED \left(Y_i - a_{k-1} X_i \Big|_{i=1}^N \right) \quad \dots (9)$$

(3) Obtain a new estimate of a for a fixed b_k using

$$a_k = MED \left(\left| X_i \right| \diamond \frac{Y_i - b_k}{X_i} \Big|_{i=1}^N \right) \quad \dots (10)$$

(4) Once a_k and b_k do not deviate from a_{k-1} and b_{k-1} within a tolerance range, end the iteration. Otherwise, go back to step (2).

Since the median and weighted median operations are both ML location estimators under the least absolute criterion, the cost functions will be non-increasing throughout the iterative procedure, that is,

$$F(a_{k-1}, b_{k-1}) \geq F(a_{k-1}, b_k) \geq F(a_k, b_k) \quad \dots (11)$$

The algorithm then converges iteratively. Since the objective function $F(a, b)$ is continuous and convex, one may readily conclude that the algorithm converges to the global minimum.

The major part of the computational power of the proposed algorithm is consumed in the weighted median operation at each iteration. Essentially, it is a sorting problem, which, for n samples, is in the order of $n \log n$. Fortunately, for this particular application, some speed-up can be achieved by not doing a full sorting every time. In [13], where the weighted median is also used as the kernel operation, a shortcut to circumvent this time-consuming full-sorting procedure is developed. The basic idea is the previous estimate can be considered close enough to the true value, thus “fine tuning” can be executed around this point by making use of the weighted median inequalities.

Consider a weighted median defined as follows:

$$a^* = \text{MED}\left(W_i \diamond Z_i \Big|_{i=1}^n\right) \\ = \arg \min_a \sum_{i=1}^N W_i |Z_i - a|$$

... (12)

where the weights $W_i \geq 0$. If we order the samples Z_i as $Z_{(1)} \leq Z_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq Z_{(N)}$, then the weight associated with the i^{th} order statistic $Z_{(i)}$ is often referred to as the concomitant $W_{[i]}$. In this way, the weighted median a^* can always be identified as $Z_{(j)}$ whose index j satisfies the following inequalities:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{j-1} W_{[i]} < \sum_{i=j}^N W_{[i]} \quad \dots (13)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^j W_{[i]} \geq \sum_{i=j+1}^N W_{[i]} \quad \dots (14)$$

We should notice that the weights W_i and samples Z_i in every LAD iteration are different. Suppose that the previous estimate a_{k-1} , which is also the output of a weighted median, corresponds to Z_j . We do not have to fully order all these samples, but classify them into two categories, the ones smaller than it and the ones larger. Check the inequalities to see if they still hold. If not, transfer the boundary sample and its weight into another group and recheck until the new weighted median output is found.

4 MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION FOR TIME SERIES MODEL

Log returns, $X_t = 100 * (\ln(P_t) - \ln(P_{t-1}))$, of financial assets often exhibit: heavy-tailed marginal distributions $P(|X_1| > x) \sim C x^{-\alpha}$, $0 < \alpha < 4$ and lack of serial correlation $\hat{\rho}_X(h)$ near 0 for all lags $h > 0$ (MGD sequence) where $|X_t|$ and X_t^2 have slowly decaying autocorrelations. Log-likelihood

$$L(\phi, \sigma) = -(n-p) \ln(\sigma / |\phi_q|) + \sum_{t=1}^{n-p} \ln f(\sigma^{-1} \phi_q Z_t(\phi)) \quad \dots (15)$$

Where

$$f_\sigma(Z) = \sigma^{-1} f(z/\sigma)$$

By choosing Laplace density the least absolute deviations

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \exp(-\sqrt{2}|z|)$$

and log likelihood becomes

$$\text{constant} - (n-p) \ln k - \sum_{t=1}^{n-p} \sqrt{2} |Z_t(\phi)| / k, k = \sigma / |\phi_q|$$

The concentrated Laplacian likelihood will be

$$l(\phi) \text{ constant} - (n-p) \ln \sum_{t=1}^{n-p} |Z_t(\phi)|$$

Maximizing $l(\phi)$ is equivalent to minimizing the absolute deviations

$$m_n(\phi) = \sum_{t=1}^{n-p} |Z_t(\phi)|$$

Assume $\{Z_t\}$ i.i.d. $f \sigma(z) = \sigma^{-1} f(\sigma^{-1}z)$ with σ a scale parameter with mean 0 and variance σ^2 . For f known, use maximum likelihood Fisher information for f unknown, use quasi-likelihood.

The limit theory for LAD estimate is

$$\hat{\phi}_{LAD} = \phi_0 + \hat{u}_n / \sqrt{n}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So that } \hat{u}_n &= \sqrt{n}(\hat{\phi}_{LAD} - \phi_0) \\ &= \arg \min S_n(u) \end{aligned}$$

$$\rightarrow \hat{u} = \arg \min S(u) \quad \dots (16)$$

For the Laplace distribution both LAD and MLE

$$\frac{\text{var}(Z_1)}{2\sigma^4 f_\sigma^2(0)} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2(\sigma^2 \hat{I} - 1)}$$

For the Student t_ν distributions

$$LAD = \frac{\text{var}(Z_1)}{2\sigma^4 f_\sigma^2(0)} = \frac{\Gamma^2(\nu/2)(\nu-2)\pi}{2\Gamma^2((\nu+1)/2)} = \frac{2(\nu-2)^2}{(\nu-1)^2} \quad \dots (17)$$

$$MLE = \frac{1}{2(\sigma^2 \hat{I} - 1)} = \frac{(\nu-2)(\nu+3)}{12}$$

Fit high order (P-th order), obtain residuals and estimate scalar by using the eqn. (17).

5 SIMULATION

This part demonstrates simulations in various situations to show the robustness of the method. We numerically compare the proposed method for Student t distribution for the samples 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1500 and 2000 for the parameter value 0.6 and 0.5 respectively. All simulations are performed by R program.

Table 1: MLE Simulation results using t-distribution

N		Asymptotic		Empirical		% coverage
		Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	
250	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.4694	0.034	0.4980	0.0398	94.3
	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.4594	0.040	0.4893	0.0235	92.2
500	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.3844	0.023	0.3929	0.0133	93.3
	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.3929	0.055	0.3835	0.0533	89.7
750	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.4024	0.033	0.3899	0.0213	90.4

	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.4210	0.024	0.3913	0.0422	93.5
1000	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.2040	0.024	0.2132	0.0233	92.7
	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.2309	0.025	0.1322	0.0173	95.1
1500	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.4594	0.035	0.4353	0.0212	96.8
	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.4504	0.046	0.4202	0.0232	90.7
2000	$\phi_1=0.6$	0.4650	0.125	0.4684	0.1321	94.8
	$\phi_1=0.5$	0.4629	0.146	0.4873	0.1424	95.5

6 RESULT

A new iterative algorithm for LAD regression is developed based on MLEs of location. A simple coordinate transformation technique is used so that the optimization within each iteration is carried out by a weighted median operation, thus the proposed algorithm is well suited for hardware implementation. Simulation shows that the new algorithm is comparable in computational complexity with the best algorithms available to date.

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